

AVOIDING USELESS CONTENT WHILE CRAWLING THE WEB

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Abstract

Practical experience with a web crawler showed that while processing huge amounts of data is not easy, the task of separating waste from precious information can be even more challenging. Here we present the basic design of a real-world web crawler and focus on practical strategies to deal with useless content.

INTRODUCTION

Crawling the web is a challenging endeavor and as such an hurdle for start-ups of web search engines (SE). An independent, open and freely available web crawler index would not only strengthen the right of free speech, decrease dependency on monopolies but also triggers innovation. Sadly so far no such index exists so that crawling is a precondition to build a SE. In this presentation we focus on *adaptive domain limiting* (ADL), a heuristic developed by the authors and used by the infotiger crawler. We define useless content (web pages) to be link farms, unlimited subdomains or content not in the focus of the SE. Obviously this definition is partially based on subjective choices.

WEB CRAWLER OVERVIEW

Figure 1 shows core components and data flow in a single web crawler node. The parser removes HTML mark-up, decides which text blocks are boilerplate and creates fingerprints of "good" text blocks. *Trace vectors* encode parsed documents in a semi-metric topic space which serve as input for similarity search or for categorization (not shown). Link analysis is used by the SE for ranking but also by the crawler in context of ADL.

Figure 1: Overview of components and data-flow of a single web crawler node.

ADAPTIV DOMAIN LIMITS

Experience with simple breadth-first search showed that the web crawler eventually becomes trapped in useless content like link spam (compare with [1]). Since a crawler has to be polite and the number of parallel requests is limited the download speed will decrease. Consequential impacts

of crawling useless content include inflating the data store and query index, reducing revisiting frequency and lowering query precision. Domain limits (DL) appear to be a promising approach to drastically reduce useless content. ADL is defined as the maximum allowed number of pages for a single domain. When starting a new crawl all DLs are set to a low number like 2000. When the limits are hit, we want to increase them *only for valuable* domains. Solely manual inspection is not feasible due to the number of hit limits on multiple crawler nodes. Increasing the DLs for domains with a SiteRank[2] higher than a given threshold (e.g. 90% if SiteRank is converted to quantiles) proved to be a good heuristic to adapt DLs for "valuable" domains.

Figure 2: Left side: Top ten domains ordered by number of indexed pages per domain after applying ADL. Right side: Top ten domains ordered by number of seen links per domain, which indicate the situation when ADLs were not applied. Data taken from a single crawler node.

CONCLUSION

We encountered two main problems with the ADL approach using SiteRank. Firstly it is vulnerable to link spam and secondly SiteRank cannot identify all useless content. The first problem could be addressed by a preprocessing step to detect and remove link spam from the document graph. The latter problem depends on the definition of useless content. For example if a SE does not want to index internet shops, the number of forward links could be a hint for detection, since shops are often bad hubs. For other unwanted content like advertising spam a deeper content-related analysis might be needed. Even with limited resources a web crawler that produces high quality input for a SE can be successfully implemented. Experience showed that one key factor are effective heuristics to reduce useless content.

REFERENCES

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